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ANALYSIS OF QUALITY LEARNING URGENCY IN ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION

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Abstract: Quality learning is learning that creates an effective and meaningful educational experience for students. Quality learning must be in accordance with the learning objectives that have been set. Every activity or material presented must support the achievement of the learning objectives that have been set. Quality learning should stimulate students to develop problem solving skills. This can be achieved by assigning assignments or projects that require analysis, synthesis, and creative thinking. Quality learning respects students' individual differences. This includes understanding students' learning styles, levels of understanding, and their specific needs, and providing appropriate support. Quality education cannot be cheap, or rather it doesn't have to be cheap or free. However, quality education does not require asking where the money will come from to form all these qualities. The government is obliged to guarantee that every citizen receives an education and guarantees access for the lower classes to quality education. In this way, schools will no longer worry about where the funds will come from, and the community will no longer have difficulty getting access to quality schools with affordable educational costs. Quality learning is an investment in students' personal and academic development. It's not just about relying on a particular method, but also about creating a learning environment that motivates, supports, and encourages students' intellectual and moral growth.

Keywords: Urgency, Quality Learning, Islamic Religious Education.

INTRODUCTION

Quality can be seen from how optimally the teacher is able to facilitate the student learning process. That every teacher or teaching staff has responsibility for the level of success of students in learning and the success of teachers in teaching. Learning can only occur if the students themselves are motivated to learn. Teachers must gradually and plan to introduce the benefits of learning as a commendable life value, so that students learn because it is based on higher values for the students' own lives. Even though this process is not simple, teachers must still try to instill a positive attitude in learning, because this is a very important part of the learning process to be able to learn.

Meanwhile, from the perspective of curriculum and learning materials, quality can be seen from how relevant the curriculum and learning materials are, able to provide various stimuli and diversified learning facilities (with diversification, application of several methods, differences). From the aspect of learning climate, quality can be seen from how great the learning atmosphere is. supports the creation of interesting, challenging, enjoyable and meaningful learning activities for the formation of educational professionalism. Meanwhile, Corey emphasizes that learning is a process in which a person's environment is deliberately managed to enable him to participate in behavior in special conditions or produce responses to certain situations. Learning is a special subset of education (Syaiful, 2003: 61).

Appropriate learning methods or strategies to achieve the learning objectives set according to existing conditions, so that the curriculum can be actualized in the learning process so that learning outcomes

are realized in students. Learning is an effort to use human resources that must be carried out continuously as long as humans live. The content and learning process need to continue to be updated according to advances in science and community culture. The implication is that if the people of Indonesia and the world want the availability of human resources who have national and international standard competencies, then the content and learning process must be directed at achieving these competencies (Kusrini et al., 2005: 128).

In general, learning outcomes will have an influence in two forms: 1). Participants will have a perspective on their strengths and weaknesses regarding the desired behavior; and 2). They find that the desired behavior has increased either one stage or two stages, so that now there will be a gap again between the current behavior and the desired behavior (Mulyasa, 2004: 169).

At this stage the teacher's activity is to assess the learning process that has been carried out. Evaluation is a tool for measuring goal achievement. With evaluation, the quantity and quality of achievement of learning objectives can be measured. On the other hand, because evaluation is a tool for measuring goal achievement, the benchmark for planning and use is the learning goal. In relation to learning, Moekijat (as quoted by Mulyasa) put forward techniques for evaluating learning knowledge, skills and attitudes.

Evaluation of knowledge learning can be done with written , oral exams and questionnaires; (2) Evaluation of learning skills, can be done with practical exams, skills analysis and task analysis as well as evaluation by the students themselves; (3) Evaluation of learning attitudes can be done with a self-completed attitude checklist, an attitude checklist adapted to the program objectives, and a semantic differentiation scale (SDS) (Mulyasa, 2004: 170).

THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Quality Learning

Learning is the process of interaction between students and educators and learning resources in a learning environment. Based on this concept, the word "learning" contains two activities, namely learning and teaching. Both activities are related to efforts to teach students to develop their intellectual potential. Quality learning at least positions students as quality students, facilitated by quality teachers, supported by a quality learning ecosystem in the context of a quality learning institution (Surakhmad, 2009: 346). Only quality learning can produce better learning. The determining components of learning quality lie in student learners, teaching programs, learning ecosystems, learning institutions, and learning facilitators.

1. Student learning

Students as actors in the learning process are often considered the most important figures in determining the quality of learning. Even though this is very inaccurate because students are not the only measure of the quality of learning. Quality students are students who are physically and spiritually ready.

2. Learning Program

The learning program includes the learning materials used. Quality material can be seen from several indicators as follows:

- a. Learning materials must be in line with the applicable curriculum.
- b. Learning materials must be in accordance with technological developments
- c. Learning materials must be in accordance with community demands.
- d. Learning materials must be appropriate to students' lives.

3. Learning Ecosystem

The learning ecosystem includes three things, namely the family ecosystem, school ecosystem and community ecosystem. These three ecosystems are related to each other so that their roles are very important and influence the quality of learning. Families with a high level of awareness of education will certainly direct their family members to excel in

learning at school. Families like this have a big contribution to the quality of students' education. Meanwhile, in terms of the school ecosystem, of course a school that creates a conducive learning atmosphere will have an impact on the quality of learning itself.

In terms of the community ecosystem, most people think that schools are a place to shelter children before they work. This is very inappropriate, because school is a place that is used to "transfer knowledge" so that children who don't know yet become aware so that the child's experience, knowledge and experiences increase or increase.

4. Learning Institute

A quality learning institution is a learning institution that is supported by various adequate facilities and infrastructure, competent teaching staff in their fields, and a solid system.

5. Learning Facilitator.

Teachers as learning facilitators must master various competencies which include pedagogic competence, personality competence, social competence, social competence and professional competence.

- a. competence is the teacher's ability to manage student learning which at least includes: understanding the insights or foundations of education, understanding students, using the curriculum or syllabus, designing learning, implementing educational and dialogical learning, using learning technology, evaluating learning outcomes, and using students to actualize their potential.
- b. personality competency which includes a personality that has faith and devotion to God Almighty, has noble character, is wise and prudent, democratic, steady, stable, mature, authoritative, honest, sportsmanlike, objectively evaluates one's own performance, develops oneself independently and sustainably.
- c. competence is a teacher's ability as part of society which includes communicating verbally or in writing politely, using communication and information technology functionally, interacting effectively with students, fellow educators, education staff, student leaders and guardians.
- d. Professional competence is the teacher's ability to master knowledge in the field of science, in accordance with the content standards of education unit programs and subjects, concepts and methods of relevant scientific, technological or artistic disciplines which conceptually cover or are coherent with the program of educational units, subjects or groups subjects taught.

Meanwhile, the remaining resources include equipment and supplies. Hope includes vision, mission, goals and objectives to be achieved. Input readiness is very necessary so that the learning process runs well. The process is said to be of high quality if the coordination and harmonization and integration of input are carried out harmoniously so as to create a pleasant learning situation, capable of encouraging motivation and interest in learning. The quality of the learning process can be measured by measuring how much student activity is involved in learning and the teacher's performance in learning.

B. Stages Toward A Quality Learning Process

Syafaruddin and Nasution stated that : " The process of a system starts from input then processed with various activities using techniques and procedures, and then produces output, which will be used by the local community" (Syafaruddin & Irwan, 2005: 43). In the context of the education system, input is represented by students, teachers, school principals, facilities, media and infrastructure. The process is represented by teaching, training, mentoring, evaluation and management. Meanwhile output includes knowledge, skills and attitudes. Regarding the components that make up the education system, in more detail, Nana Syaodih ,

stated that " input components are classified into three, namely (1) raw input , namely students which include intellectual, physical-health, social-affective and peer group . (2) Instrumental input, including educational policies, educational programs (curriculum), personnel (principals, teachers, TU staff), facilities, media, and costs, and (3) Environmental input, including the school environment, family environment, society, and social institutions, work units. "Meanwhile, the process components include: teaching, training, mentoring, evaluation, extracurricular, and management (Syaodih et al., 2006: 7). Furthermore, output includes knowledge, personality and performance.

Apart from the above, related to the process stages of learning, it is also inseparable from the competencies that a teacher must have, teachers have at least three basic competencies, namely personality competency, competency in mastering teaching materials, and competency in teaching methods (Ramayulis, 2001: 110). These three competencies should be understood and mastered so that teachers can carry out their duties well. To be able to manage a good learning program, there are three main things that teachers must pay attention to, namely the planning/preparation stage, the implementation stage, and the assessment/evaluation stage.

factors are components of education, one of which is interconnected and supports each other, because if one of these elements does not meet educational quality standards, then it is likely that the quality of learning will not be achieved properly . Teachers as educators also greatly influence the quality of learning, therefore teachers must be able to carry out their duties professionally. These three will be discussed as follows:

1. Planning Stage.

Good learning activities always start from a thorough plan. Careful planning will show optimal results in learning. Planning is the process of preparing something that will be implemented to achieve a predetermined goal. The implementation of the plan can be structured based on needs within a certain period according to the wishes of the planner. However, what is more important is that the plans made must be implemented easily and on target. Likewise with learning planning, what is planned must be in accordance with educational targets. Teachers as subjects in making learning plans must be able to prepare various teaching programs according to the approaches and methods that will be used.

In the context of educational decentralization along with the realization of equal distribution of quality educational outcomes, subject competency standards are needed that can be accounted for in the local context, national and global. In general, the teacher must fulfill two categories, namely having capability and loyalty, namely the teacher must have ability in the field of science he teaches, have theoretical abilities regarding good teaching, from planning, implementation to evaluation, and have teacher loyalty, namely loyal towards teacher tasks not only in class, but before and after class (Rosyada, 2004: 112). So, the difference is only a gradual difference, not an essential difference.

So that the learning process can be carried out effectively and efficiently, the steps taken by the teacher in the planning stage are formulating instructional objectives or learning objectives (Djamarah, 1994: 56). This goal will later be used as a guide for teachers in learning activities. Other elements that must be present in planning a teaching are formulating experience objectives, determining teaching materials, student learning activities, and teaching methods and teaching tools (Djamarah, 1994: 81).

2. Implementation Stage

In carrying out teaching, the teacher is guided by the teaching preparation that has been previously formulated. However, in the learning interaction process teachers must also pay

attention to teaching principles, namely motivation, cooperation and competition, correlation and integration, individuality and evaluation (Suparta & Ali, 2003: 72-78).

3. Evaluation Stage

In teaching, there needs to be an evaluation/assessment so that the learning process can be observed as far as possible, the success of the teaching and the students' mastery of the lessons given so that evaluation can be carried out on learning outcomes and the learning process. Assessment of the teaching process is carried out to determine the effectiveness of teaching strategies . implemented, the methods and media used, teaching materials and the assessment system carried out by the teacher. As stated by Ahmad Rohani, "Assessment functions as feedback in remedial teaching". So that with the assessment, improvements in teaching design and teaching implementation strategies can be made that are adapted to developments in science.

The assessment that needs to be carried out again is the assessment of student learning outcomes. According to Syaiful Bahri Djamarah, "Assessment is useful for knowing to what extent students have achieved the predetermined learning objectives" (Djamarah, 2010: 105). So that by assessing learning outcomes the teacher knows whether the teaching is successful or not. Tools for assessing learning outcomes include tests and test books, while test procedures can be carried out in formative and summative forms. Thus, assessments of the teaching process and results need to be carried out continuously so that teachers always make efforts to renew their teaching actions, so that the quality of the teaching process is expected to improve student learning outcomes.

C. Determinants of Quality Learning

1. Quality of Physical Facilities

Physical facilities are facilities that include the physical body of a body involved in the world of formal education. The building is good and the use of learning media, library books and laboratories meets standards. Adequate information technology and so on.

2. Teacher Quality

Teachers must have adequate professionalism to carry out their duties as stated in article 39 of Law No. 20/2003, namely planning learning, implementing learning, assessing learning outcomes, providing guidance, conducting training, conducting research and carrying out community service. If we look at the ratio of teachers to students, the good ratio between teachers and students is 1:22 in elementary schools, 1:16 in junior high schools, and 1:12 in high schools/vocational schools. The distribution of teachers must also be evenly distributed to every region or school that has a shortage of teachers. Although teachers and tutors are not the only determining factor in educational success. However , teaching is the central point of education and qualifications, as a reflection of quality, teaching staff have a huge influence on the quality of education for which they are responsible.

3. Teacher Welfare

Teacher welfare has a role in creating the quality of education. With a good income, teachers have professionalism in their work and can avoid doing side jobs. Such as teaching at another school , giving tutoring in the afternoon, becoming a motorbike taxi driver, boiled noodle seller, book/LKS seller, cell phone credit seller, and so on. By avoiding the above, teachers can focus on the quality of the education provided.

4. Student achievement

With such conditions (good physical facilities, teacher quality, and teacher welfare) student achievement becomes more satisfying.

5. Equalization of Educational Opportunities

The opportunity to obtain education is not limited to a particular school level. By providing educational services, failure in coaching will not hinder the use of human resources as a whole. Therefore, appropriate educational equality policies and strategies can overcome the problem of unequal opportunities in the world of education.

6. Affordable Education Costs

Quality education is expensive. This sentence often appears to justify the high costs that people have to pay to receive a quality education. The current high cost of education cannot be separated from government policies that implement SBM (School Based Management). In reality, MBS in Indonesia is interpreted more as an effort to mobilize funds. Therefore, the School Committee/Education Council, which is an SBM organ, is always required to have an entrepreneurial element.

Like companies, schools are free to seek capital to invest in educational operations. The coordinator of the NGO Education Network for Justice (ENJ), believes that privatizing education means that the government has legitimized the commercialization of education by handing over responsibility for providing education to the market. That way, schools will have the autonomy to determine their own costs for providing education.

D. The Impact of Quality Learning on Child Development

1. Experiencing Conscious and Intentional Change

This change in behavior is a change that occurs due to awareness and deliberate factors carried out by the individual concerned. Because it is done consciously and deliberately, the individual also knows and is aware of the changes that occur within him due to the changes he has made to his life.

2. Experiencing Continuous Change

The increase in knowledge and skills in education possessed by each individual is of course a continuation of the knowledge and skills that have been obtained previously. Likewise, the knowledge, attitudes and knowledge obtained will become the basis for the sustainable use of the knowledge that will be obtained by the individual in the future.

3. Experiencing Functional Changes

Every change in behavior that occurs can be used for the good and interests of the individual concerned, both for present and future interests, which can be applied in the future.

4. Experiencing Active Change

To get new behavior and of course better than the previous one, the individual concerned will try to change himself. For example, if you want to have skills in a field, then the individual must strive or do business in the desired field.

5. Experiencing Permanent Changes

Children's education functions in the short, medium and long term. Because education lasts a lifetime. Behavioral changes obtained from a quality learning process tend to remain and will become an inherent or integral part of the individual.

6. Experiencing Changes in Intellectual Skills

One of the important things about the good quality of this education is that it can direct each individual to gain intellectual skills. If children are active in the educational process, it is possible that children will have skills in interacting with their surrounding environment.

7. Experiencing Changes in All Aspects of Children's Lives

In general, if a child follows the educational process well, it is not only education and knowledge of lessons that will increase. But all aspects of himself will change for the better. Because if you want to change for the better, then all habits, behavior and traits that were previously not good must be changed little by little so that the overall change process within the child can change in a better direction. So the quality of education is very important to shape a child's character.

CONCLUSION

The quality of learning is one of the benchmarks that can determine the success or failure of the teaching process. So, being able to measure the level of quality and success of an education are several indicators that can be seen from the intellectual, affective, emotional and psychomotor-practical cognitive dimensions that can be developed in a balanced way. The concept of improving the quality of learning is one element of the new paradigm of education management. This paradigm contains the main attributes, namely being relevant to the needs of the community using graduates, a conducive academic atmosphere in the implementation of study programs, institutional commitment from leaders and staff to effective and productive organizational management, sustainability of study programs, and selective program efficiency based on feasibility and adequacy. These dimensions have a very strategic position and function for designing and developing quality-oriented education delivery efforts in the future. Quality learning must also be able to adapt to developments in the world and student needs. Flexibility in learning design is key.

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